

of such reaction. Since the observed current density is considered to be proportional to the rate of production of charge carriers, the logarithmic plot of current density vs m mole of H_2O should yield a straight line with $\log_{10} k$ as an intercept and n as a slope of the line.

In order to test the validity of the above approximation for the kinetic law the data of all the three types of cell have been utilised. For type I, a plot of $\log_{10} Id$ vs \log_{10} m moles of H_2O (where Id is the current density) has been shown in Fig. 2. The straight line suggests that the charge carrier generation in the system is of a first order at each temperature. This behaviour is observed even at higher temperatures. The rate

Fig. 2. Logarithmic plot of Id vs H_2O adsorbed at different temperature; cell Cu/CuCl/Pt.

constants at four different temperatures were estimated from the intercepts.

Similar data were plotted for type II and type III cells and showed that the reaction in each case obeys first order kinetics. This, however, is not true at higher H_2O concentration.

Fig. 3. Arrhenius plot of rate constant.

Finally, the Arrhenius plot of the type I data appears to be significantly informative. The Arrhenius plot of rate constant has been shown in Fig. 3 and this plot shows an activation energy of 0.34 eV. This activation energy favours the positive hole charge transport in carrying the current as proposed here.

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Polarographic Behaviour of Ga(III), In(III) and Ge(IV) in Aqueous Mixtures of Organic Solvents

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THOUGH the polarographic behaviour of various inorganic depolarizers in aqueous mixtures of organic solvents has been studied¹⁻¹⁶, studies on polarographic behaviour of Ga(III), In(III) and Ge(IV) in aqueous mixtures of organic solvents are still lacking. With this in view a polarographic study of the influence of aqueous mixtures of methanol, ethanol, acetone, acetonitrile and dimethylformamide on the kinetics of electrode reactions of these depolarizers has been undertaken. The influence of increasing concentrations of organic solvents on the electrode reactions of the depolarizers has been explained in terms of the values of kinetic parameters αn_a and $k_{f,h}^0$ calculated by Koutacky's method¹⁸⁻²¹.

Experimental

Stock solutions of Ga(NO₃)₃·H₂O (Fluka, A.R.), In(NO₃)₃·3H₂O (E. Merck, GR) and GeO₂ (Fluka, A.R.) were prepared in conductivity water. The concentration of each of the depolarizers in the final solutions to be polarographed was maintained at 1.0 × 10⁻³ M. NaClO₄ (0.1 M) was used as the supporting electrolyte in the case of Ga(III) and Ge(IV) while 0.1 M KCl was used in the case of In(III). A manual polarograph (Toshniwal CLO 2) in conjunction with a polyflex galvanometer (Toshniwal PL 50) was used. The characteristics of d.m.e. have been mentioned in the subsequent Tables. All measurements were made at 25° ± 0.1°. Requisite amount of Triton X-100 (1.0 × 10⁻³%) was added to suppress the maxima of Ga(III) and Ge(IV). Since no maxima appeared in the case of In(III) under the chosen experimental conditions, addition of Triton X-100 was avoided. Purified nitrogen was used for removing the dissolved oxygen. The number of electrons, n, involved in the electrode reduction of each of the depolarizers was determined by millicoulometric¹⁷ method. 'n' was found to be 3 for Ge(III) and In(III) and 4 for Ge(IV). Knowing the value of n, the diffusion-coefficient (D) of the depolarizers was calculated by Ilkovic equation at different percentages of organic solvents. The rate constant, k_{f,h}, at different potentials was calculated by the method of Koutecky¹⁸⁻²¹. The kinetic parameters, αn_a and k_{f,h}⁰, were obtained from the variation of k_{f,h} with applied potential²⁷. Throughout the measurements, the current at the end of the drop (i.e., the maximum current) was recorded as according to Meites²⁸ maximum current should be measured if the kinetic parameters for an irreversible wave are to be calculated by Koutecky's method.

Results and Discussion

Ga(III), In(III) and Ge(IV) give well-defined waves in presence of the aqueous mixtures of organic solvents used. However, in the case of Ga(III) the wave becomes drawn out at higher percentages of methanol, ethanol and acetonitrile. Similarly, in the case of Ge(IV) the wave becomes drawn out at higher percentages (> 50%, v/v) of methanol and acetonitrile.

The waves of all the depolarizers are diffusion-controlled as revealed by the linearity of i_d vs h^{1/2}_{corr plots and their passing through the origin.}

Various criteria of irreversibility²²⁻²⁵ indicate that the electrode reactions of Ga(III) and Ge(IV) are irreversible in the presence of organic solvents. In the absence of organic solvents the electrode reaction of In(III) is reversible in 0.1 M KCl. But with the addition of increasing amounts of organic solvents the electrode reaction becomes irreversible.

Tables 1, 2 and 3 include the values of polarographic characteristics and kinetic parameters

(αn_a and k_{f,h}⁰) for the electrode reactions of Ga(III), In(III) and Ge(IV) as a function of the percentage of the organic solvents in the aqueous mixtures.

Influence of increasing amounts of organic solvents on the kinetics of the electrode reactions of Ga(III), In(III) and Ge(IV) :

(i) *Electrode reaction of Ga(III) :* A perusal of Table 1 reveals that at lower percentages (≤ 5%, v/v) of methanol, ethanol and acetonitrile both αn_a and k_{f,h}⁰ increase thereby suggesting²⁶ that the irreversible electrode reaction of Ga(III) becomes less irreversible. But at higher percentages of these solvents (≥ 5%, v/v) the kinetic parameters record a decrease in their values thereby indicating that the irreversible electrode reaction of Ga(III) is rendered more irreversible at higher percentages of the organic solvents.

TABLE 1—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS AND KINETIC PARAMETERS FOR THE ELECTRODE REACTIONS OF Ga(III) IN PRESENCE OF AQUEOUS MIXTURES OF METHANOL, ETHANOL AND ACETONITRILE

m = 1.89 mg/sec ; t = 3.1 sec ; m^{2/3}t^{1/6} = 1.84 mg^{2/3}sec^{-1/3}
(in 0.1M NaClO₄, open circuit) ; h_{corr.} = 72.17 cm

Percentage of organic solvent (v/v)	i _d (μA)	-E _{1/2} V (S.C.E.)	Slope (mV)	D × 10 ⁶ (cm ² /sec)	αn _a	k _{f,h} ⁰ (cm/sec)
0	10.10	1.13	132	7.34	0.43	7.8 × 10 ⁻¹⁰
<i>Methanol</i>						
5	10.03	1.10	100	6.62	0.54	2.7 × 10 ⁻⁹
10	7.39	1.12	135	3.60	0.40	2.0 × 10 ⁻⁹
25	6.34	1.14	150	2.64	0.36	8.6 × 10 ⁻¹⁰
40	4.75	1.16	155	1.22	0.35	1.4 × 10 ⁻¹⁰
50	Wave drawn out					
<i>Ethanol</i>						
5	10.03	1.09	105	6.62	0.52	9.3 × 10 ⁻¹⁰
10	8.09	1.12	120	4.31	0.45	7.7 × 10 ⁻¹⁰
25	7.04	1.13	130	3.26	0.42	4.0 × 10 ⁻¹⁰
40	5.37	1.14	135	1.90	0.40	1.6 × 10 ⁻¹⁰
50	Wave drawn out.					
<i>Acetonitrile</i>						
5	8.09	1.10	127	4.30	0.49	8.6 × 10 ⁻¹⁰
10	6.51	1.12	139	2.79	0.39	1.2 × 10 ⁻¹⁰
25	Wave drawn out					

(ii) *Electrode reaction of In(III) :* With the addition of increasing amounts (≥ 10%, v/v) of methanol, ethanol, dimethylformamide and acetone the reduction of In(III) at d.m.e. becomes totally irreversible. It is evident from Table 2 that both αn_a and k_{f,h}⁰ decrease with increasing percentages of these organic solvents. This indicates that the electrode reaction of In(III) tends to become more irreversible with the increase in the percentage of organic solvents in the mixtures.

(iii) *Electrode reaction of Ge(IV) :* A perusal of Table 3 shows that at lower percentages (≤ 10%, v/v) of methanol, ethanol and acetonitrile both αn_a and k_{f,h}⁰ increase and thereafter decrease. It

TABLE 2—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS AND KINETIC PARAMETERS FOR THE ELECTRODE REACTION OF In(III) IN PRESENCE OF AQUEOUS MIXTURES OF METHANOL, ETHANOL, DIMETHYLFORMAMIDE AND ACETONE

$m=3.72$ mg/sec ; $t=3.2$ sec ; $m^{1/2}t^{1/2}=2.84$ mg^{1/2}sec^{-1/2} (in 0.1M KCl, open circuit) ; $h_{corr}=72.17$ cm

Percentage of organic solvents (v/v)	i_d (μ A)	$-E_{1/2}$ (S. C. E.)	Slope (mV)	$D \times 10^6$ (cm ² /sec)	αn_a	$k_{f,h}^0$ (cm/sec)
0	18.80	0.53	21.4	9.48	—	—
<i>Methanol</i>						
10	16.68	0.52	44.1	7.67	1.37	9.6×10^{-7}
25	14.55	0.53	46.8	5.83	1.23	7.0×10^{-7}
50	12.06	0.55	58.8	4.00	1.15	3.0×10^{-7}
75	10.99	0.55	83.3	3.33	0.92	9.2×10^{-8}
<i>Ethanol</i>						
10	12.06	0.53	78.1	4.00	0.69	5.6×10^{-7}
15	9.58	0.54	68.2	2.53	0.63	1.2×10^{-7}
20	6.39	0.55	96.1	1.12	0.56	7.6×10^{-8}
50	4.08	0.57	97.2	0.46	0.55	2.9×10^{-8}
<i>Dimethylformamide</i>						
10	17.38	0.54	40.0	8.32	1.35	1.7×10^{-6}
25	12.59	0.55	41.6	4.37	1.30	8.4×10^{-6}
50	8.87	0.60	47.6	2.17	1.13	7.4×10^{-6}
75	6.21	0.69	58.6	1.06	0.93	3.9×10^{-6}
<i>Acetone</i>						
2	16.28	0.55	47.6	7.30	1.10	6.6×10^{-7}
4	11.09	0.56	71.4	3.39	0.76	1.5×10^{-7}
6	7.22	0.58	83.6	1.44	0.65	9.2×10^{-8}
8	6.16	0.59	89.2	1.04	0.61	6.1×10^{-8}
10	3.17	0.61	92.3	0.28	0.58	2.0×10^{-8}

TABLE 3—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS AND KINETIC PARAMETERS FOR THE ELECTRODE REACTION OF Ge(IV) IN PRESENCE OF AQUEOUS MIXTURES OF METHANOL, ETHANOL AND ACETONITRILE

$m=3.59$ mg/sec ; $t=3.2$ sec ; $m^{1/2}t^{1/2}=2.84$ mg^{1/2}sec^{-1/2} (in 0.1M NaClO₄, open circuit) ; $h_{corr}=72.17$ cm

Percentage of organic solvents (v/v)	i_d (μ A)	$-E_{1/2}$ (S. C. E.)	Slope (mV)	$D \times 10^6$ (cm ² /sec)	αn_a	$k_{f,h}^0$ (cm/sec)
0	22.06	1.41	130	7.54	0.40	4.0×10^{-11}
<i>Methanol</i>						
5	22.42	1.34	90	7.78	0.60	8.0×10^{-11}
10	20.93	1.35	120	6.79	0.45	9.4×10^{-11}
25	17.74	1.38	125	4.87	0.43	7.2×10^{-11}
40	16.67	1.38	127	4.30	0.42	3.9×10^{-11}
50	Wave drawn out					
<i>Ethanol</i>						
10	23.77	1.34	100	8.75	0.54	7.4×10^{-11}
25	20.22	1.37	120	6.33	0.52	6.2×10^{-11}
50	18.45	1.38	130	5.27	0.48	3.2×10^{-11}
75	17.03	1.39	135	4.49	0.42	1.6×10^{-11}
<i>Acetonitrile</i>						
10	17.38	1.41	125	4.68	0.43	4.4×10^{-11}
25	15.97	1.45	128	3.95	0.42	8.4×10^{-12}
50	14.55	1.45	130	3.28	0.41	3.1×10^{-12}
75	Wave drawn out					

follows from this that at lower percentages of these organic solvents the irreversible electrode reaction of Ge(IV) becomes less irreversible while at higher percentages it tends to become more irreversible.

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Temperature Coefficient of Excess Volumes for Binary Solutions of *m*-*o*- and *p*-Xylenes in Tetrahydrofuran

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IN continuation of our work¹⁻³ on thermodynamic properties of binary solutions, Oswal and Bakore⁴ recently reported the excess volumes V^E for solutions of *m*-, *o*- and *p*-xylenes in tetrahydrofuran